

THE PEDAGOGICAL PROFESSION AND ITS PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES

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Abstract. *Professional competence implies not merely the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the mastery of integrative knowledge and actions within each independent field. It also requires the continuous enrichment of professional knowledge, the study of new information, the ability to recognize important social demands, to search for new data, process them, and apply them in one's professional activity.*

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INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of market relations, strong competition in the labor market requires every specialist to possess professional competence and to continuously improve it in order to remain competitive. What, then, is competence? What qualities form the basis of professional competence? What competence-related qualities should a teacher develop and demonstrate? This section discusses these and related issues.

The English term “competence” literally denotes “ability.” In its broader sense, however, it refers to the effective use of theoretical knowledge in practice, as well as the demonstration of a high level of professional qualification, mastery, and talent in one's activity.

The concept of “competence” entered the field of education as a result of psychologists' scientific research. From a psychological perspective, competence refers to a specialist's ability to behave appropriately in non-standard situations and unexpected circumstances, to engage in effective communication, to adopt new approaches in interactions with opponents, to perform uncertain tasks, to use contradictory information, and to possess a plan of action in progressively developing and complex processes.

Professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary to carry out professional activity, as well as the capacity to apply them in practice at a high level.

Professional competence does not imply merely the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but rather the mastery of integrative knowledge and actions within each independent field. It also requires the continuous enrichment of professional knowledge, the study of new information, the ability to recognize important social demands, to search for new data, process them, and apply them in one's professional activity.

- Professional competence becomes particularly evident in the following situations:

- in complex processes;
- when performing uncertain tasks;
- when using contradictory information;
- when being able to develop a plan of action in unexpected situations.

A specialist who possesses professional competence:

- consistently enriches their knowledge;
- assimilates new information;
- deeply understands the demands of the time;
- searches for new knowledge;
- processes it and effectively applies it in practical activity.

The following qualities constitute the foundation of professional competence:

Figure 1. The following qualities underlying professional competence

Below is a brief explanation of the essence of the qualities underlying professional competence.

1. Social competence — the possession of skills and abilities to actively participate in social relations and to engage in communication with subjects involved in professional activity.

2. Special competence — readiness to organize professional-pedagogical activity, to rationally solve professional tasks, to realistically evaluate the results of one’s activity, and to consistently develop knowledge, skills, and abilities. This competence includes psychological, methodological, informational, creative, innovative, and communicative components, which reflect the following:

1. **Psychological competence** — the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants in the educational process, and to identify and eliminate negative psychological conflicts in a timely manner;
2. **Methodological competence** — the ability to organize the pedagogical process methodologically, correctly determine forms of educational activity, select appropriate methods and tools, and apply them effectively;
3. **Informational competence** — the ability to search for, collect, select, process, and effectively use necessary and useful information in the information environment;

4. **Creative competence** — a critical and creative approach to pedagogical activity and the ability to demonstrate one’s creative skills;
5. **Innovative competence** — the ability to propose new ideas aimed at improving the pedagogical process, enhancing educational quality, and increasing the effectiveness of upbringing, as well as successfully implementing them in practice;
6. **Communicative competence** — the ability to maintain sincere communication with all participants in the educational process, including students, to listen attentively, and to exert a positive influence on them.

3. Personal competence — achieving continuous professional growth, improving one’s qualification level, and demonstrating internal potential in professional activity.

4–5. Technological competence — mastery of advanced technologies that enrich professional-pedagogical knowledge, skills, and abilities, and the ability to use modern tools, equipment, and technologies.

6. Extreme competence — the ability to make rational decisions and act appropriately in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological failures) and when pedagogical conflicts arise.

In the works of pedagogical scholars, various aspects and structural components of competence have been identified and studied, allowing for a broader and more detailed pedagogical understanding of this concept. According to S. E. Shishov, competence can be defined as:

- a general capability based on knowledge, experience, values, and dispositions acquired through learning;
- the ability to establish a connection between knowledge and situations and to find solutions appropriate to the problem (competence can only be considered as such when it is manifested in a particular situation; otherwise, it remains a hidden potential).

L. M. Dolgova, P. V. Simonov, and others consider competence to be the ability to act based on acquired knowledge. Unlike “knowledge, skills, and abilities,” which imply actions similar to given models, competence presupposes independent activity based on universal knowledge. Dolgova emphasizes that competence represents knowledge and skills manifested in social practice when socio-cultural requirements and societal demands are placed on educational outcomes.

According to V. V. Bashev, competencies are individual abilities that manifest themselves in the transfer of these abilities to new conditions when circumstances change. Their fields of application determine their specificity (mathematical, linguistic, political, etc.). A competent person functioning effectively in society must be able to:

1. analyze the situation in which they find themselves;
2. establish communication with others;
3. make decisions;
4. organize individual and collective actions to implement decisions;
5. master new methods of activity.

Thus, competence can be interpreted as capability, readiness, and opportunity, as well as the result of certain actions. In other words, competence is an activity-related category manifested in professional, social, and other forms of activity aimed at fulfilling assigned tasks.

Competence represents a certain level of development of skills and professional experience necessary for an individual to function successfully in society in general and in the professional sphere in particular, as well as to interact effectively with surrounding objects and subjects.

A number of studies have examined professional competence specific to teachers and its distinctive features. Among them are the works of A. K. Markova and B. Nazarova.

According to A. K. Markova, the professional competence of a teacher consists of the following structural components:

1. Special (professional) competence — the ability to organize professional activity at a high level;
2. Personal competence — self-development and self-expression;
3. Social competence — the ability to organize collaborative activities;
4. Individual competence — self-management, professional development, and innovation.

In the context of Uzbekistan, professional competence specific to teachers has also been studied. According to B. Nazarova, it includes:

1. Special (professional) competence — organization of professional activity at a high level;
2. Autocompetence — the ability to develop oneself socially and professionally;
3. Social competence — collaborative organization of professional activity and social responsibility;
4. Extreme professional competence — the ability to function in unexpected situations.

The concept of “pedagogical mastery” was scientifically substantiated in the 1980s–1990s and began to be taught as an independent subject in higher education institutions. With the introduction of the subject “Pedagogical Technology,” the foundations of pedagogical mastery were incorporated into its content. Before discussing the professional mastery of preschool educators, it is appropriate to clarify the concepts of “mastery” and “pedagogical mastery.”

Mastery — the ability to perform a task or activity at a high level with exceptional skill and without difficulty.

Pedagogical mastery — the teacher’s ability and competence to organize and manage the pedagogical process with a high degree of skill from organizational, methodological, psychological, and subjective perspectives.

Mastery (from the Arabic “*mahorat*” — skillfulness, proficiency, dexterity) is the ability to perform a task or activity at a high level, with exceptional skill and without difficulty.

Pedagogical mastery is the teacher’s possession of the ability and competence to

Pedagogning mahorati bevosita kasbiy-pedagogik faoliyatda ko‘rinadi. SHu sababli u A teacher must deeply understand the general essence of the pedagogical process, be aware of the fundamental principles that play a leading role in this process, and thoroughly master the mechanisms for effectively organizing pedagogical activity. As an active participant in the educational process, a teacher’s pedagogical mastery reflects their personality, professional experience, civic status, professional standing, sufficient command of pedagogical techniques, and the individuality of their professional activity. Pedagogical mastery represents an integrated system that includes a number of essential qualities. In particular:

Important components of pedagogical skills

The basis of pedagogical skill is pedagogical knowledge.

Pedagogical knowledge is the ability of a teacher to organize professional activities in accordance with existing social requirements, legal norms and standards, and the level of professional training.

The professional knowledge of a teacher includes the ability to establish a subjective relationship with a student; the ability to consistently perceive the essence of pedagogical processes, pedagogical reality; the ability to study the foundations of world pedagogical culture and national pedagogical experience, apply them to one's activities on the basis of integration; constant awareness of innovative innovations; generalization of personal experiences and transfer to students; professional dedication and mastery of pedagogical technologies are manifested.

At the heart of pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical reflection (Latin "reflexio" - return, reflection) is also prominent. In the sources, the concept of "reflection" is interpreted as "a person's theoretical activity aimed at understanding and comprehending his own actions and their foundations; a separate activity of cognition", "understanding the essence of personal experiences, feelings and thoughts through thinking."

Pedagogical reflection is the teacher's understanding of the essence of the individual's consciousness, tasks, values, interests, motivations, thinking, perception, decision-making, emotional reactions, actions, etc.

A teacher's ethics are also clearly reflected in his or her work. Moreover, pedagogical ethics are considered one of the important requirements and factors ensuring the success of educational and upbringing processes.

Pedagogical ethics is a system of moral requirements imposed on a teacher regarding his or her attitude towards himself or herself, his or her profession, society, students, and other participants in the educational process.

These requirements are an important factor in the development of the pedagogical work and activity process organized by the teacher. The system of pedagogical etiquette requirements is of particular importance in the fulfillment of professional duties by the teacher, his moral obligations to society, the pedagogical community and the student.

Pedagogical etiquette plays a leading role in clarifying the essence of such main categories as pedagogical ethics and moral values reflected in the pedagogical process. All universal and national moral values also play a leading role in the activities of the teacher.

1. Professional and pedagogical duty. Universal moral values such as goodness and evil, justice and injustice, honesty and deceit, mercy and cruelty, sincerity and darkness, patriotism and patriotism, peace and war serve as a kind of measure in the life, lifestyle and behavior of people. In pedagogical activity, a teacher must be able to glorify these values and organize his activities based on them. In addition, each teacher must be able to fully understand his professional and pedagogical duty and organize practical actions to fulfill it. A teacher's clear determination of what tasks he must perform before society, its members, the pedagogical and student community, and what principles he must rely on in fulfilling his professional and pedagogical duty, creates the opportunity to independently determine his position as an individual, a specialist, and a citizen. If he can organize his professional activities in accordance with existing ethical principles, then his self-esteem will increase and he will gain confidence in his own strength. This will encourage the teacher to achieve new achievements. If a teacher understands his professional and pedagogical duty, but cannot organize it in accordance with existing moral requirements, then, first of all, he loses self-respect and cannot appreciate himself as a person.

2. Pedagogical justice. "The concept of justice is determined by certain historical conditions and socio-economic relations. The moral aspect of justice means treating people equally in interpersonal relations, not violating each other's dignity, and observing the rules of morality." In addition, justice serves to characterize the interrelationship between human dignity and its recognition by society, existing moral rules and obligations. Pedagogical justice has its own characteristics, it reflects the level of moral education (noble deeds, determination, seriousness, humanity) of the teacher in assessing the behavior of his students in accordance with their merits before the community.

3. Pedagogical obligation (pedagogical deontology). One of the important categories of pedagogical ethics - the concept of pedagogical obligation - includes the requirements and moral guidance and instructions imposed by society on the teacher's personality, his fulfillment of a number of pedagogical obligations. In organizing professional activities, a teacher must be able to fulfill the following obligations: to perform specific labor tasks, mainly intellectual labor tasks; to properly organize interaction with students, their parents, colleagues; to deeply understand his personal attitude to his chosen profession, to students and the pedagogical community, and to society. Among the pedagogical responsibilities, it is also necessary to demonstrate a creative attitude to the organization of professional activities, self-demandingness, striving to enrich professional knowledge and improve pedagogical skills, establishing a respectful and demanding relationship with students and their parents, mastering the skills of positive resolution of complex pedagogical conflicts, etc.

4. Pedagogical reputation. The pedagogical reputation of a teacher guarantees the effectiveness of the professional activities organized by him.

Pedagogical reputation is the moral status of a teacher recognized by students, their parents, the pedagogical team, and society.

Relying on the reputation gained by the teacher, he controls the behavior of students, gains their trust. Pedagogical reputation also reflects the moral, ethical and pedagogical-psychological preparation of the teacher. The level of reputation possessed by the teacher is determined by his deep knowledge, intelligence, skills, attitude to his work, etc. Pedagogical ability. How effective and successful the pedagogical process is depends on the teacher's pedagogical ability. In one of the sources, the concept of "ability" is interpreted as follows: an individual psychological characteristic that ensures that a person can easily master any activity.

Ability is divided into two groups: general and special abilities. "While general abilities are manifested in the main types of individual activity, abilities that are manifested in certain types of professional activity (mathematical, technical, musical, visual arts, literature (poetry and prose), physical training, etc.) are called special abilities... One of the leading characteristics of abilities is the creative imagination of the essence of things and phenomena."

Pedagogical abilities are characteristics that are important for ensuring the rational organization and conduct of pedagogical activities by a teacher and the effective implementation of practical tasks.

Conclusion

The following are the priority characteristics of pedagogical ability. Priority characteristics of pedagogical ability:

- pedagogical tact (the ability of the teacher to observe the existing moral principles, rules of behavior in communication with students in various forms of activity, to approach them correctly);
- pedagogical observation (the ability of the teacher to notice even the most simple features inherent in students);
- love for students (to love them, to show kindness, to share their inner experiences, feelings, hopes, aspirations in life, to care for them in difficult situations);
- the need to transfer knowledge (the desire as a teacher to pass on the knowledge he has to students).

REFERENCES

1. Markova A.K. Psixologiya professionalizma. – M.: Znanie, 1996.
2. Muslimov N.A. Bo'lajak kasb ta'limi o'qituvchilarini kasbiy shakllantirish /Monografiya. – T.: Fan, 2004.
3. Muslimov N.A., N.Karimova. Kasb ta'limi o'qituvchilarining amaliy kompetentligini shakllantirish texnologiyasi. – T.: "Iqtisodiyot" nashriyoti, 2012.
4. Qodirova F "Maktabgacha pedagogika" T.: «Tafakkur», 2019 y.
5. SH.A.Sodikova. "Maktabgacha pedagogika". "Tafakkur sarchashmalari" T.: 2013 y.
6. N.M.Kayumova "Maktabgacha pedagogik" TDPU nashriyoti T.: 2013 y.
7. Xasanboeva O.U. va boshy. Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagogikasi. T.: Ilm ziyo. 2006.
8. Kozlova S.A., Kulikova T.A. Doshkolnaya pedagogika. M.: Akademiya. 2002 g.
9. www.tdpu.uz

10. www.pedagog.uz
11. www.Ziyonet.uz